

Time Modulated Array and Time Variant Filter Techniques to Reduce Receiver Hardware Complexity and Power Consumption

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Abstract— Sustainability is a key goal for 6G, which focuses on minimizing the environmental impact of network operations through energy-efficient designs, agile architectures, and renewable energy sources. While traditional hardware is designed to optimize its performance with maximum functionalities to cover all possible scenarios, this often results in high system complexity. Therefore, scalable system performance with good power efficiency and moderate hardware complexity is key to 6G sustainability. This paper explores power reduction and performance/functionalities trade-offs combining two recently proposed time-variant CMOS radio receiver techniques: 1) a Time Modulated Array (TMA) technique that re-uses a single 4-element phased array to concurrently receive data streams from 5 different beam directions; 2) a time-interleaved Analog Finite Impulse Response Filter (AFIR) with embedded frequency translation realizing the selectivity to separate the 5 data streams. The aim of the paper is to assess the realistically achievable power and hardware complexity savings and relevant trade-offs with radio performance.

Keywords—PHY, CMOS, Software Defined Radio, RF Receiver, IF filtering, Analog FIR filtering, Filtering by Aliasing, Harmonic Rejection, Power efficiency, Anti-alias filtering, filter selectivity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Green Information and Communication Technologies are a focus area for 6G, and relevant organizations in the field like ETSI, 3GPP, IEEE, ITU-T and IA-6G initiated activities targeting sustainability (for an overview, see [1] and [2]). Sustainability has many aspects, but clearly, PHY hardware complexity and power consumption is one of them. This paper explores two recently published techniques validated in silicon [3],[4] that can be combined to realize a reconfigurable beamforming receiver. We show how the same hardware can be re-used to cover different use scenarios with a strongly varying number of users and spectrum/data-rate requirements. Prior MIMO [5] and carrier aggregation [6] receiver architectures typically focus on either one channel at a time or multiple carriers but lack adaptability to changing scenarios.

For example, in busy environments like shopping malls or train stations, there are many users during peak times, resulting in a high demand for data communication. Conversely, during quieter periods, demand significantly decreases, and the spectrum becomes much less congested. Individual user requirements may also vary hugely. We will explore options to reduce hardware complexity and power consumption by significant factors exploiting temporarily reduced requirements. This will be done by combining two recently proposed techniques: a Time Modulated Array (TMA) [3] and a time-interleaved Analog FIR filtering (AFIR) supporting frequency translation [4]. This combination can act as a concurrent multi-beam multi-stream receiver for multiple users with a one-wire IF interface. It can also be configured as a traditional analog beamformer array with one beam and wider bandwidth. Essentially, we can adapt the RF receiver array to different user/beam scenarios with the same hardware.

Fig. 1. TMA mode of the proposed reconfigurable receiver frontend with four antennas mapping five incident concurrent beams from five different directions to five different IF frequencies.

As shown in Fig. 1, TMA can map multiple concurrent beams from different directions to different IF-frequencies, where the spacing in IF is equal to the Time Modulation frequency f_{TM} [3]. The AFIR with embedded frequency translation selects one of the IF channels, filters it and converts it to baseband, relaxing the dynamic range and sample rate of

the ADCs. This allows for “performance on demand”, as AFIR slices can be switched off if not needed. Moreover, if the spectrum is empty because of few users, AFIR filter requirements can be relaxed, and further, the TMA clocking signals can be disabled. Overall, this results in a significant hardware and power reduction. We will show that TMA can support five beams with a single-beamformer, effectively saving a factor of five in hardware complexity and power while also simplifying the data transport from the array to the baseband processing chip and allowing for scalability to a large-sized array. For the AFIR filter, we will show that a factor of five in hardware and power can be saved for relaxed interference scenarios compared to a high-performance AFIR filter.

It is worth mentioning that multiple array systems have been reported recently based on extensions of the TMA architectures, such as combining TMA and Butler matrix to generate a large number of beams (4-element array for 20 concurrent beams) [7], performing Nyquist-rate fast beam switching for multibeam phased array receiver [8], and using pulse width modulation for independent beam controls in the multi-beam TMA system [9]. The analyses and techniques reported in this paper are potentially applicable to these extended TMA systems as well.

Fig. 2. Noise behavior of the receiver frontend in the TMA mode (MCM).

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section II introduces the reconfigurable receiving beamformer frontend with a discussion on its noise behavior in the TMA mode and the TMA frequency selection criteria. Section III discusses the AFIR technique with embedded frequency translation and the possibilities of reducing hardware and power, and the resulting trade-offs in filter suppression, harmonic suppression, and alias suppression. Section IV combines the techniques in a simulation model based on hardware extraction results and estimates achievable performance, while section V draws conclusions.

II. RECONFIGURABLE RECEIVER FRONTEND

The front end of the proposed reconfigurable beamforming receiver (shown in Fig. 1) has two modes of operation: 1) Single Carrier Mode (SCM), where one beam with the full bandwidth is assigned to a single user for a high data-rate communication link; 2) Multi Carrier Mode (MCM) to *concurrently* serve multiple users via multiple beams. Based on the application scenario, one of the two modes can

be configured using the same shared hardware. In MCM, the switches of the channels are periodically ON/OFF modulated to perform the TMA operation and concurrently receive multiple incident beams at the same RF frequency, while mapping them to different IF frequencies. On the other hand, in SCM, all the frontend switches are continuously in the ON-state, allowing the reception of a high data-rate single beam with enhanced array gain. In both modes, phase shifters are utilized to steer the TMA multiple beams altogether in MCM or arbitrarily steer the high data-rate beam in SCM.

A. TMA concept and operation

The TMA operation for a 4-element array can be explained with the aid of Fig. 1. The four elements of the array are sequentially ON/OFF modulated in a periodic manner, in which each element is only turned ON for one-fourth of the time modulation period (T_{TM}). Assuming same phase-shifter settings, under this operating regime, as studied in [3], the 4-element TMA is capable of concurrently receiving five same-RF-frequency independent beams from five different spatial angles given by $\theta = 0^\circ, \pm 30^\circ, \text{ and } \pm 90^\circ$, and mapping them with ideally infinite cross-beam isolation to five different IF frequency components given by $f_{IF}, f_{IF} \pm f_{TM}$, and $f_{IF} \pm 2f_{TM}$ respectively. That is, using a low-complexity single-wire interface, the TMA performs space-to-frequency mapping and allows simultaneously serving up to five users, each with one-fifth of the total operating bandwidth. On top of the TMA operation, phase shifters are utilized to steer the five beams altogether.

B. Noise behavior

The noise behavior of the proposed receiver array frontend in the TMA mode (MCM) can be evaluated with the aid of Fig. 2. By taking a time-domain approach, as shown in Fig. 2, it can be seen that the noise contribution of each channel appears at the combiner’s output for only one-fourth of the time-modulation period. That is, at any given time instant, the combiner’s output is only affected by one channel’s noise contribution. Therefore, under the assumptions that: (a) the noise contribution of the TMA switch is negligible (a reasonable assumption with a sufficiently large LNA gain), (b) the noise sources of the four channels are sample functions of the same white random process, and (c) the noise random process is stationary (i.e., the statistics of the noise do not

Fig. 3. IF-Frequency grid in MCM for RF-channel’s bandwidth (B_{ch}) = 150 MHz and TMA-frequency (f_{TM}) = 450 MHz.

change over time), it turns out that the noise spectral density

statistics at the combiner's output are identical to that of one channel. Hence, the SNR reduction due to TMA of 6dB is mainly caused by changing beamforming gain, not noise.

C. Choice of TMA-frequency

The TMA-frequency (f_{TM}) in MCM should be judiciously selected to preserve the multi-beam signal fidelity by satisfying the Nyquist criteria and avoiding inter-beam aliasing. More rigorously, given a channel's bandwidth B_{ch} , a transition-bandwidth B_{tr} , the choice of f_{TM} must satisfy:

$$\frac{B_{ch}}{2} + B_{tr} + \frac{B_{ch}}{2} < f_{TM}. \quad (1)$$

In this work, B_{ch} is set at 150 MHz, and B_{tr} is set at twice the RF channel's bandwidth (300 MHz), which is deemed to be a feasible choice for the time-varying filter, as studied in Section III. Accordingly, f_{TM} is set at 450 MHz, resulting in the IF-frequency grid that is shown in Fig. 3.

III. IF-FILTERING AND FREQUENCY TRANSLATION

This section briefly discusses how the IF signals in Fig. 3 are separated and conditioned for easier A/D conversion using so-called "Filtering and Frequency Translation by Aliasing" (FTA) [4]. Section III-A discusses the block diagram of the FTA. Section III-B discusses the circuit-level implementation of the FTA-based $g_m C$ receiver. Finally, Section III-C discusses the programmability of the FTA receiver.

Fig. 4. Block-level implementation of FTA-based receiver.

A. FTA-based IF receiver

FTA uses time-discrete AFIR signal processing controlled by digital weights. It realizes programmable higher-order filtering and frequency translation with programmable center frequency (f_c), bandwidth (BW), transition band and stop-band attenuation [4]. Both band-pass filtering (BPF) and low-pass filtering (LPF) are possible by modifying the digital weights in memory. Fig. 4 shows the block diagram of the FTA-based receiver. The IF-input $x(t)$ is sampled and multiplied by the time-varying filter coefficient $\alpha(t)$, then summed over filter length (N) and finally sub-sampled (f_{sub}) to achieve high-order filtering and a low sample rate, i.e. relax ADC requirements and reduce the digital signal processing rate. For the BPF, the f_{sub} frequency translates the input to zero or low IF, depending on the f_{IF} and f_{sub} [4]. I and Q paths are implemented to resolve signal components across multiple Nyquist zones. The time-varying filter coefficients change at rate f_s , the input sampling frequency of the FTA receiver.

FTA [4] and FA "Filtering by Aliasing" [10], [11], [12] allow for some (controlled) level of aliasing to realize better filter selectivity and better hardware efficiency. There are two aliasing mechanisms in our FTA receiver:

1. Aliases from sampling in the time-varying multiplier (f_s)

2. Aliases due to sub-sampling (f_{sub})

The sampling aliases are suppressed by the RF BPF filtering and a low-pass anti-alias filter between the RF- and IF-circuits. Aliases due to sub-sampling are rejected by the AFIR filtering [10], [11], [12] and can be mitigated by increasing the effective sub-sampling frequency in a time-interleaved architecture [4]. The minimum sub-sampling frequency ($f_{sub,min}$) to ensure that aliases are attenuated to the filter's stop-band attenuation is [4]:

$$f_{sub,min} \geq f_{stopband} + BW_{BB} \quad (2)$$

where $f_{stopband}$ is the stop-band frequency, and BW_{BB} is the baseband bandwidth. The number of time-interleaved paths (M) is then determined by

$$M = \frac{f_{sub,min} \times N}{f_s} \quad (3)$$

B. Circuit implementation

Fig. 5. Circuit level implementation of proposed $g_m C$ -based FTA IF receiver with LPF and BPF filter coefficients and timing diagram.

Fig. 5 illustrates the circuit-level implementation of the proposed $g_m C$ -based FTA IF receiver (I and Q), providing a high-impedance voltage-sensing load to the TMA RF-stage rather than low-ohmic switched-capacitor [4] or resistive [11] loading. It consists of a time-varying g_m , active integrator and sub-sampler to achieve higher-order filtering. The time-varying g_m is implemented using a 10-bit binary weighted g_m operating at sample rate f_s . The LSB of the time-varying g_m is chosen to be $(1/2^{10})$ mS to achieve a cascaded Noise Figure (NF) of 4 dB. The active integrator is implemented with multi-stage OPAMP, which provides virtual ground at the output node of the time-varying g_m . The FTA operates in four phases: multiplication, integration, sub-sampling and reset. First, the input V_{IN} is multiplied by varying the time-varying g_m according to the LPF/BPF coefficients, as shown in Fig. 5. For the BPF, negative coefficients are implemented by switching the polarity switches (Φ_p) between V_{IN+} and V_{IN-} . In the second phase, the multiplied input is integrated into the capacitor (C_{int}) thanks to the virtual ground at the output node of the time-varying g_m . Next, after completing N cycles, the sub-sampling (Φ_{sub}) is activated, and the output ($V_{OUT}[n]$) is

read out. Finally, the reset (Φ_{res}) occurs post-sub-sampling, lasting for five time periods to ensure proper settling time.

In this implementation, five ($M = 5$) time-interleaved paths are chosen to achieve an ‘‘In Band Alias Suppression’’ (IBAS) equal to the targeted filter performance (Transition band $-1 \times BW_{RF}$ (RF bandwidth) and stop-band attenuation -55 dB). Additionally, an extra 6th path allows for readout without affecting filtering.

C. Receiver programmability

The proposed g_mC FTA receiver is designed to operate in two distinct modes, as depicted in Fig 6:

Fig. 6. Different operating modes of the proposed IF receiver. (a) Single Carrier Mode (SCM): All five FTA blocks operate at f_c in a time-interleaved manner. (b) Multi Carrier Mode (MCM): Each FTA block operates at different center frequencies ($f_{c1} - f_{c5}$).

SCM: This mode accommodates only a single RX channel and delivers high-performance IBAS and NF. All five RX modules operate at a single center frequency f_c in a time-interleaved manner, as shown in Fig. 6. The effective sub-sampling frequency is improved by 5x, which brings IBAS > 55 dB. In BPF configuration, sinusoidal multiplication (see Fig. 5) introduces signal attenuation that degrades NF. Alternatively, a passive hard-switched downconversion mixer can be used, which has less attenuation and better NF but has a poor Harmonic Rejection (HR) (a 50% duty-cycle square wave has a 3rd harmonic only 9.5 dB weaker than the 1st harmonic).

MCM: This mode supports M separate RX channels operating concurrently but at reduced performance in terms of IBAS and NF. Each RX module operates at a distinct center frequency ($f_{c1} - f_{c5}$) with a sub-sampling rate reduced by a factor of 5. This reduction limits the maximum achievable baseband bandwidth (Nyquist criterion - $f_{sub}/2$). To achieve this strict bandwidth requirement ($f_{sub}/2$), the stop-band attention needs to be traded off to approximately 30 dB. Furthermore, due to impedance scaling (which is downscaled by a factor of 5), the power/channel (by a factor of 5) reduces, but the RX NF increases. Similar to SCM, the NF in the case

of MCM can be improved by utilizing square wave mixing instead of sinusoidal mixing, although this comes with a trade-off in HR [4].

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

This section presents the simulation results for the reconfigurable receiver frontend followed by the FTA/AFIR IF-receiver.

A. Reconfigurable Frontend

A macro model was developed for the proposed reconfigurable receiver frontend at 15 GHz, which is derived from the Silicon chip realization in [3]. Simulations are performed using Cadence Spectre. The operating RF and LO frequencies (f_{RF} and f_{LO} respectively) are taken as 15 GHz and 14.025 GHz, respectively. The LNA has a gain of 24 dB and a noise figure of 2 dB. The phase shifter covers the whole 360 $^\circ$ phase range with a step of 5.625 $^\circ$ (6 bits of resolution). A 1-dB insertion-loss TMA switch is used, and the mixer and frontend LPF performance is estimated from the Silicon realizations in [13] and [14] respectively. Both modes of the receiver frontend are simulated to verify the functionality of the proposed reconfigurable frontend.

In the TMA-mode (MCM), f_{TM} is set at 450 MHz based on the selection criteria discussed in Section II-C, and practical rise/fall-time values of 20 ps are used for the time modulation clocks. Two scenarios are tested in Fig.7 to demonstrate the multi-beam capabilities of the TMA-mode, where the array factor for each test scenario is constructed across an incidence-angle range from -90° to 90° (measured from the array’s broadside). In case A (shown in Fig. 7(a)), same settings are used for the phase shifters (i.e., the five TMA beams are not steered), while in case B (shown in Fig. 7(b)), the phase shifters are configured to steer the fundamental beam (at 975 MHz) from 0° to 10° .

Fig. 7. Simulated array factors of the proposed reconfigurable receiver frontend in the TMA-mode (MCM): (a) case A where same phase shifter settings are used, and (b) case B where the phase shifters are configured to steer the fundamental beam from 0° to 10° .

A test scenario is also performed for the single-beam SCM and is shown in Fig. 8, where the phase shifters are configured to steer the array towards an incidence angle of 10° with an array gain of 6 dB. These simulation results in Fig. 7 and 8 clearly demonstrate the multi-beam and single-beam capabilities that are achieved in MCM and SCM respectively using the proposed reconfigurable receiver frontend. However, it is worth noting the trade-offs between supporting a single-user with the total bandwidth with an enhanced array gain of 6dB (SCM) versus concurrently supporting five users (MCM). As 6dB lower array gain reduces SNR by 6dB, we lose 2 bits Shannon capacity, which gives for our system 20% lower data rate (QAM-64 vs. QAM-256). Still aggregate data rate may improve as we will see later.

Fig. 8. Simulated array factor of the proposed reconfigurable receiver frontend in the high-speed single-beam mode (SCM) where the phase shifters are configured to steer the array towards 10° .

B. FTA IF receiver

Fig. 9. Simulated BPF TF (Spectre RF PSS and PXF) for $f_s = 4$ GHz, $f_c = 1000$ MHz in SCM ($N = 30$) and MCM ($N = 25$) configurations.

A macro model of the proposed FTA-based g_mC receiver with model parameters derived from silicon chip realizations [4], [12] is simulated in cadence spectre RF PSS and PXF to verify its functionality and estimate performance. The sampling frequency of the time-varying g_m is fixed at $f_s = 4$ GHz, and the f_c is changed by modifying the filter coefficients. An ideal $1:\sqrt{2}$ balun is used to convert single-ended (50-ohm port) input to differential inputs (V_{IN+} and V_{IN-}). Fig. 9 shows the simulated BPF TF in SCM ($N = 30$) and MCM ($N = 25$) configurations for $f_c = 1000$ MHz across the first Nyquist zone. In the case of high-performance SCM, all five RX modules operate in a time-interleaved manner, thus achieving $f_{sub,scm} = 666.67$ MHz with $BB_{RF} = 300$ MHz. Thanks to the 10-bit quantization level and five paths, the receiver in SCM mode achieves a stop-band attenuation of 55 dB at only $1 \times BW_{RF}$ frequency offset, 55 dB HR and 55 dB IBAS. In the case of the moderate-performance MCM, a

single RX module with $f_{sub,mcm} = 160$ MHz, achieves $BB_{RF} = 150$ MHz with 30 dB stop-band attenuation at $1.2 \times BW_{RF}$ frequency offset, 30 dB HR and 3 dB IBAS. Fig. 10 shows the simulated BPF TF in MCM with each RX module concurrently operating in distinct f_c . It is important to note that this approach is most effective when the radio spectrum is unoccupied or not heavily used.

Fig. 10. Simulated BPF TF (Spectre RF PSS and PXF) in MCM configuration with each RX module operating at distinct center frequencies ($f_{c1} = DC$ (LPF), $f_{c2} = 525$ MHz, $f_{c3} = 975$ MHz and $f_{c4} = 1425$ MHz and $f_{c5} = 1875$ MHz).

Fig. 11. Simulated NF (Spectre RF PSS and PNOISE) for $f_s = 4$ GHz, $f_c = 1000$ MHz for BPF and LPF in SCM ($N = 30$) and MCM ($N = 25$) configurations.

Fig. 11 shows the simulated PSS and PNOISE for BPF/LPF for an arbitrarily chosen IF $f_c = 1000$ MHz. In both SCM and MCM cases, the LPF configuration shows 3 dB better NF than the BPF configuration. This improvement is attributed to the absence of sinusoidal mixing. In the case of SCM with $N = 30$, $f_{sub,scm} = 666.67$ MHz, the input frequency range of 1000 to 1150 MHz is frequency translated to a low IF range of 333.34 to 183.34 MHz. Conversely, for MCM with $N = 25$, $f_{sub,mcm} = 160$ MHz, the input frequency range of 1000 to 1040 MHz is frequency translated to low IF 40 to 80 MHz. Similarly, the frequency range 1040 to 1075 MHz is frequency translated to low IF 80 to 45 MHz. Consequently, the NF for both SCM and MCM, in a BPF configuration, is presented for their respective low IFs. Additionally, due to impedance scaling (downscaled by a factor of 5), the NF for MCM is higher than that for SCM.

The total power consumption for g_mC -based FTA can be estimated using measured silicon implementation of the previous FTA receiver [4]. In the case of digital memory and clock dividers, prior silicon implementations consumed approximately 30 mW at a sampling frequency of 1 GHz. When scaled to $f_s = 4$ GHz, we estimate the power

consumption to be around 120 mW. Furthermore, the g_m/I_d ratio is estimated at 12.8 V^{-1} . The total g_m , which includes time-varying g_m and OPAMP, required for all five TI paths is 125 mS, resulting in an approximate power consumption of 9 mW. Therefore, the proposed gmC-based FTA's total power consumption is approximately 129 mW.

Table I summarizes the performance of the reconfigurable frontend followed by the FTA-based gmC receiver in both SCM and MCM configurations. Thanks to the programmability of the time-varying architectures, the receiver in the MCM can support five concurrent beams with 5x savings in hardware and power at the cost of 2x lower bandwidth per beam and slightly larger NF. In the case of SCM, the 4x higher hardware adds 6 dB higher SNR and hence improves spectral efficiency compared to MCM (QAM 256 vs QAM 64). Still, more users can be served concurrently in the case of MCM, and the aggregate data rate increases from 2.4 to 4.8 Gbps at lower power per user.

TABLE I PERFORMANCE SUMMARY OF THE FRONTEND FOLLOWED BY THE FTA RECEIVER IN BOTH SCM AND MCM CONFIGURATIONS

Frontend	SCM	MCM
Number of array elements	4	4
Number of concurrent beams	1	5
Array gain factor per beam [dB]	6	0
Total Estimated power [mW]	200	201
Estimated power per beam [mW]	200	40.2
FTA		
Number of RX channels	1	5
Number of time-interleaved paths	5	1
Sampling frequency [MHz]	4000	4000
BW _{RF} [MHz]	300	150
Transition band	1 x BW _{RF}	1.2 x BW _{RF}
Stop-band attenuation [dB]	55	30
Harmonic Rejection (HR) [dB]	55	30
In-band Alias Rejection (IBAS) [dB]	55	3
System Noise Figure [dB]	LPF	4
	BPF	7
Total Estimated power [mW]	129	129
Estimated power/channel [mW]	129	25.8
System		
Modulation scheme	256-QAM	64-QAM
Aggregate Data capacity [Gbps]	2.4	4.5

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper explored possibilities to reduce hardware complexity and power consumption of a TMA beamforming receiver architecture. A 4-antenna-element beamforming receiver is used to concurrently receive 5 data streams from 5 different beam directions, adding just 4 switches to realize time modulation (=TMA), which maps individual beams to individual IF-frequencies spaced by f_{TM} . This saves 5x hardware and 5x power, albeit at the cost of lower array gain per beam and lower bandwidth per beam. Moreover, only a single-wire interface between the TMA-array and IF-processing chips is needed. An IF-FIR filtering technique with embedded frequency translation can separate the data streams to individual ADCs. This allows for scalable performance, while ADC dynamic range and sample rate requirements are also greatly relaxed. If the radio spectrum is not heavily used, up to a factor of 5 in hardware and power

reduction is possible, provided the reduced selectivity, harmonic rejection and aliasing rejection are acceptable. The claims are verified by cadence spectre RF simulations using circuits validated by silicon realizations.

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